
Erosion of Human Values in J. M. Coetzee's *Disgrace*

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Abstract:

J.M. Coetzee (John Maxwell Coetzee) is a South African-born writer, academic, and Nobel Laureate best known for his profound and often unsettling novels that explore themes of morality, power, identity, and human suffering.

*J.M. Coetzee's *Disgrace*, is a multilayered story set against the backdrop of turbulent political situation in post-apartheid South Africa. The erosion of human values is a central theme in J.M. Coetzee's *Disgrace*, explored through the personal, societal, and historical lenses of post-apartheid South Africa. Coetzee uses the protagonist, David Lurie, and the changing dynamics of power, morality, and identity to illustrate how traditional human values—such as dignity, responsibility, empathy, and justice—are undermined or redefined in a society undergoing radical transformation.*

*In the apartheid Africa the Europeans or the White rulers considered the blacks as slaves. They were insulted, humiliated, abused and punished. The inhuman treatment saw the retaliation of this. The democracy in South Africa emerged with a sinister design to attack the Whites. After coming to power the blacks started crushing the pride and honor of the whites. Coetzee has depicted misuse of democracy in South Africa. Democracy advocates law and order. It never meant to disgrace, insult or exploit the minority on the issues of race, religion, language and ethnicity. But the minority is always at the mercy of the majority. The novel pictures the deep erosion of the human values. The research paper attempts to focus on the erosion of the human values in Coetzee's *Disgrace*.*

Keywords: *Democracy, Human Values, Erosion, Disgrace, Insult, Abuse, Misuse etc.*

Erosion of human values has led to dehumanization of the powerless by the powerful. The people, who are powerful insult, abuse as well as assault the one who are less powerful. The history of mankind tells that from ages man has been dehumanizing other man. The weak are oppressed by the strong. In this process of oppression human values are eroded. The Kings/ Rulers are always considered as supreme. They have exercised supremacy over their subjects. There are examples of how the aboriginals are dehumanized. The natives especially the Blacks or the Negroes of the African countries experienced

dehumanization at the hands of the Europeans for centuries. The Blacks were tortured, abused, exploited and treated inhumanly by the White rulers. The blacks struggled and won freedom from the tyrannical rule of the whites. After coming to power the blacks started crushing the pride and honor of the whites. Coetzee has depicted misuse of democracy in South Africa. Democracy advocates law and order. It never meant to disgrace, insult or exploit the minority on the issues of race, religion, language and ethnicity. In this novel the whites have to struggle for their pride and honor.

Disgrace is a subtle multilayered story of Professor David Lurie, Lucy and Petrus set against the backdrop of turbulent political climate of South Africa, after the end of apartheid rule. The writer of the novel J. M. Coetzee born in Cape town, is a witness to the grim reality of the life in south Africa. He has observed the ugly and cruel face of democracy that prevailed in South Africa. In the novel Disgrace he tries to depict the reality in a very honest and sensitive manner.

David Lurie one of the major characters is the representative of the White minority in South Africa. He is the professor of English at the Technical University. But he is a womanizer, a man with carnal desire. He has married twice and twice divorced. To satisfy his sexual hunger he visits Soraya, a prostitute on every Thursday and enjoys sex with her. He feels satisfied with her. One day David happens to see Soraya in market along with her two sons and Soraya also sees David. After that incident their relation becomes rather indifferent. Soraya leaves the work with an excuse of her mother being ill. She doesn't inform Lurie, nor does she give him her address or contact number. Soraya breaks the relation without any prior intimation. Lurie appoints a spy to find out the true life of Soraya but she does not respond to him. He tries to contact her but she refuses to recognize him and warns him not to call on telephone. After Soraya Lurie hire another whore called Dawn but she fails to satisfy him. Without sex his life becomes deserted and lusterless. The above incidents depict the dehumanization of the weaker sex that is woman. It is the honour killing of a woman, who is forced to become a sex worker for living. Soraya actually wants an honorable life like common women but circumstances force her to live a double life. David Lurie is a twice divorced man, he rejects Dawn too. Isn't this entire terrible thing that a Male uses a female as an object of his entertainment? Lurie shifts himself

from one woman to another. If he is not satisfied he discards them. David Lurie does not stop here. He tries to trap a young student called Melanie. He observes her physical posture and gesture. He becomes successful in seducing Melanie. The following dialogue of David Lurie depicts his view, "Why? Because a woman's beauty does not belong to her alone, It is part of the bounty she brings into the world. She has a duty to share it" (16). Here we notice the relation between the seasoned professor and a first year student is certainly unethical and unacceptable. In fact he should have kept himself away from the personal life of the girl student. His behavior as a professor is unworthy. But nothing can stop him.

After this incident Melanie decides to quit her studies. Her father requests David to look into the matter and persuade Melanie to continue the course. He never dreamt that a professor might be the cause of his daughter's trouble. When Melanie's father comes to know of David's behavior towards Melanie, he gets a great shock. He is emotionally wrecked. He is unable to bear the animalistic passion of the academician in the University.

The novelist presents the pathetic, helpless father. Before he talks to the professor, he takes a pause and gathers himself takes a deep breath. He begins by laying a heavy stress on the word, He is shocked by the behavior of the educated, moreover an academician. In case of Melanie David is guilty. His carnal lust forced him to violate the honour of a student, who is entrusted to him for learning both by the University as well as the parents. The teacher is a guide, mentor of a student. Here the violation of a girl student's honour is an act of dehumanization on the part of a Professor teacher. It is shameful and disgraceful. Professor David's act disgraces the profession of the teacher as well as the seat of learning that is the college or the university. The students are angry and

protest against the professor for his dehumanizing act. The message written everywhere in the university campus; “YOUR DAYS ARE OVER CASANOVA” (43)

In the other part of the novel David Lurie’s daughter Lucy living in Salem, a small village in Eastern Cape becomes the victim of political turmoil in Africa. In the absence of Petrus her farm assistant, dog man and neighbour Lucy is raped by three black natives. They enter her house with an excuse to use her telephone for making an urgent call. Lucy knows that Erasmuskraal is a remote area and perhaps the speakers are true. She trusts them and allows to use her telephone. As soon as she unlocks the door they over power her, David is locked in the lavatory. He is doused with alcohol and set fire. He is beaten. Lucy is raped mercilessly in presence of David. The valuables are stolen even they take off David’s car. Moreover they killed Lucy’s dogs.

Coetzee has pictured the pathetic condition of the whites in independent South Africa. The whites are exploited by the blacks. This has become very common, just the order of the day. Here the writer shows the mockery of Democracy. The Democracy is paralyzed by its people. The Whites are in minority. They have to live at the mercy of the Blacks. Democratic laws have been made toys in the hands of the powerful blacks. David convinces Lucy to consider herself lucky to have escaped with her life and also be thankful that you are not prisoner in the car bottom of donga with a bullet in her head.

After the incident David insists of making a police complaint. She tells David to complain about the stolen things and the car. She does not want to mention about the rape. She knows that the system is helpless as the criminals have godfathers. When Petrus returns he shows the least concern for Lucy. In fact he throws a party for his success. In that party Lucy recognizes the

boy among the three; he is the brother of Petrus’ second wife. But David and Lucy cannot do anything. The Whites have become voiceless and helpless in the power structure of South Africa. They have to struggle for their honour. They are insecure in an independent country. They have to live under the fear psychosis as they are in minority. Lucy had never witnessed such horrendous activity. It was done with such personal hatred. That was what stunned her more than anything. She didn’t understand the reason for their hatred.

The behavior, attitude and purpose of the black natives are to dehumanize the whites. It is not only the physical dehumanization of one’s body, but it is an important example of the dehumanization of the virtues of sympathy and humanity. It is to be condemned. It has disgraced the human values as well as the humanity. The dehumanization is the result of the politics of hatred. The blacks hated the white race. Their grudge was against the white skin of Lucy and David. The human values are deteriorated on the basis of the racial discrimination.

David suggests to Lucy to quit the place. But she is pregnant and has decided to give birth to the child. She further reveals that she has already suffered the trauma and aborted the child. Instead she is now going to accept Petrus’ proposal and surrender herself, the farm and everything to Petrus. In short she will become Petrus’ third wife. Lucy has realized that if she wants to stay in South Africa she should have the protection of the black native. She says: Say I accept his protection...If he wants me to be known his third wife, so be it. As his concubine, ditto. But then the child becomes his too. The child becomes part of his family....I will become a tenant on his land’ (204).

Being the representative of the minority white race and without any democratic privilege, the disgrace of David Lurie and Lucy is completed. They have to

undergo humiliation, abuse, torture and degradation of life. The dehumanization of David Lurie and Lucy is presented in the following words of David.

How humiliating, 'he says finally. 'Such high hopes, and to end like this'....

"With nothing. Not with nothing but. With nothing. No cards, no weapons, no property, no rights, no dignity."

'Like a dog'

"Yes, like a dog'. (205)

Coetzee's novel does not merely depict the personal downfall of a man, but maps the disintegration of the broader moral landscape in post-apartheid South Africa. The Erosion of human values-manifested through power, desire, and violence are a consequence of the shifting power dynamics and social upheaval in post-apartheid South

Africa. David Lurie's fall from grace and the violence experienced by Lucy reflect a broader societal decline, highlighting the enduring impact of colonialism.

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